

THE IMMUNE STATUS OF THE ORGANISM OF BULLS UNDER CADMIUM LOAD AND THE EFFECTS OF CORRECTING FACTORS

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Abstract

Man-made pollution of the environment through food chains has a significant impact on animal productivity and product quality. The studied environmental pollutant, cadmium, is classified as an extremely dangerous heavy metal. That is why the study of the effect of this toxicant on the immune system of the body of young cattle and the development of its correction is relevant. Research in this direction is relevant and has significant prospects. The experiments were carried out on six-month-old bulls, a Ukrainian black-and-white dairy breed. The bulls were subjected to a cadmium load by feeding cadmium chloride with feed at a dose of 0.04 mg/kg of animal body weight. It has been established that the cadmium load in bulls had an immunosuppressive effect on the activity of the immune system, which indicates a decrease in the indicators of humoral and nonspecific parts of the immune defense. To prevent the development of chronic cadmium toxicosis, experimental animals were given the feed additive Metisevit at a dose of 0.36 g/kg of feed and the liposomal preparation Butaintervit at a dose of 5 ml per animal. These preparations contributed to an increase in nonspecific resistance, in particular, an increase in the bactericidal and lysozyme activity of blood serum, phagocytic activity and phagocytic index with a simultaneous decrease in the level of circulating immune complexes in their blood. Under the experimental cadmium load, the best effect on the immune defense of the organism of bulls was exerted by the combined use of the feed additive Metisevit and the liposomal preparation Butaintervit. These changes in the body of young cattle are associated with the complex action of both the components of the feed additive and the liposomal preparation. The liposomal form of Butaintervit has a more pronounced and lasting effect. Metisevit and the liposomal preparation Butaintervit complement the prescribed therapy and, when used together with a cadmium load, show high therapeutic efficacy.

Keywords: heavy metals, cadmium, immune system, milk thistle, interferon.

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1. Introduction

Heavy metals as priority environmental pollutants have attracted the attention of toxicologists and ecologists in recent decades [1, 2]. Cadmium occupies a special place among them, which is due to its long half-life, high storage capacity, carcinogenic and mutagenic effects [3, 4].

Cadmium is capable of high levels of accumulation, initiates free radical oxidation of lipids, causes damage to membrane lipoproteins, inactivation of enzymes, and inhibition of cell division [5, 6].

When ingested orally into animals, about 95 % of cadmium accumulates in the intestine, with 75 % in the soluble fraction of the intestinal endogenous copper complex, apparently involved in its adsorption. In the liver, 80 % of cadmium binds to endogenous metallothionein [7, 8].

When administered with feed, cadmium leads to metabolic disorders, loss of resistance to infectious diseases, decrease in animal productivity, slows down growth and development, which leads to a decrease in animal slaughter rates [9, 10].

Of particular importance is the problem of the effect of heavy metals on the immune system, since it plays a leading role in maintaining health and is recognized as one of the most sensitive to the action of adverse factors, even in relatively low concentrations [11, 12].

That is why the aim of the work was to investigate the immune status of the organism of bulls under the cadmium load and the action of the feed additive Metisevit and the liposomal preparation Butaintervit.

2. Materials and methods of research

Experimental studies were carried out on 15 six-month-old bulls of the Ukrainian black-and-white dairy breed in the farm of Tsana R, Ivanovtsi village, Zhydachiv district, Lviv region. For the experiment, three groups of 5 animals each were formed. The bulls of the control and both experimental groups were fed cadmium chloride with feed at a dose of 0.04 mg/kg of animal body weight for a month.

Metisevit was additionally given for bulls of the first and second experimental groups (TU U 10.9-00492990-004:2014) in the diet at a dose of 0.36 g/kg of feed for 30 days. The composition of the feed additive includes metifen, selenium and vitamin E.

On the first and seventh days of the experiment, bulls of the second experimental group were additionally injected with the liposomal preparation Butaintervit (TU U 21.2-00492990-010:2016). The preparation Butaintervit) at a dose of 5 ml per animal. The composition of this preparation includes butaphosphate, interferon, spotted milk thistle and vitamins.

The research materials are described in more detail in the article [13].

3. Results

The conducted studies have shown that phagocytic activity of neutrophils in the blood of young cattle of the control group is inhibited under cadmium load on the 20th and 30th days of the experiment, where, respectively, this indicator decreased by 6 and 5.1 % relative to the initial ones (Table 1).

Table 1

Phagocytic activity of neutrophils in the blood of bulls under cadmium load and the action of corrective factors, % ($M \pm m$, $n=5$)

Blood test time (days)	Group of animals		
	Control	Experiment 1 Metisevit	Experiment 2 Metisevit+Butaintervit
Initial values	57.2±1.58	57.1±1.53	56.8±1.74
1 day	57.1±1.85	57.3±1.81	57.6±1.82
5 days	57.5±2.05	57.4±1.66	58.1±1.94
10 days	55.6±2.25	57.1±2.10	58.4±1.93
15 days	54.0±1.50	56.3±1.51	58.0±1.56
20 days	51.2±1.14	56.1±1.49*	57.8±1.69*
30 days	52.1±0.95	56.3±1.37*	57.7±1.71*

When Metisevit was used in bulls of the first experimental group, a probable increase in the phagocytic activity of neutrophils was found on the 20th and 30th days of the experiment, so on the 20th day of the experiment this indicator increased by 4.9 %, and on the 30th day – by 4.2 % relative to the control group. Additional use of the liposomal preparation Butaintervit contributed to the growth of phagocytic activity in the blood of the second experimental group up to 57.8±1.69 %. On the 30th day of the experiment in the blood of this experimental group, the phagocytic activity of neutrophils remained at the same level.

It should be noted that when using the liposomal preparation Butaintervit, the phagocytic activity of neutrophils in the blood of animals was slightly higher than in the experimental group, which were fed only Metisevit.

At the beginning of the experiment, the phagocytic index in the blood of the control and experimental groups fluctuated within physiological limits. With a cadmium load in the bulls of the control group on the 5th day of the experiment, an increase in the phagocytic index to 9.91 ± 0.42 units was established. This increase may be due to the protective-compensatory reaction of the bull organism to the feeding of cadmium chloride. Subsequently, a decrease in the phagocytic index was found in the blood of bulls in the control group. So, on the 15th day of the experiment in the blood of the bulls of the control group, a decrease in the phagocytic index by 12.8 % was found, and on the 20th day of the experiment – by 16.7 %, respectively (**Table 2**).

Table 2Phagocytic index of the blood of bulls under cadmium load and the action of Metisevit and Butaintervit, units ($M \pm m$, $n=5$)

Blood test time (days)	Group of animals		
	Control	Experiment 1 Metisevit	Experiment 2 Metisevit + Butaintervit
Initial values	9.72 ± 0.24	9.73 ± 0.30	9.72 ± 0.27
1 day	9.76 ± 0.31	9.74 ± 0.38	9.81 ± 0.32
5 days	9.91 ± 0.42	9.81 ± 0.29	9.85 ± 0.28
10 days	8.75 ± 0.39	$9.84 \pm 0.31^*$	$9.90 \pm 0.25^*$
15 days	8.47 ± 0.28	$9.58 \pm 0.29^*$	$9.85 \pm 0.30^{**}$
20 days	8.10 ± 0.35	$9.24 \pm 0.26^*$	$9.80 \pm 0.30^{**}$
30 days	8.58 ± 0.37	$9.34 \pm 0.30^*$	$9.77 \pm 0.21^*$

Feeding the Metisevit supplement with feed contributed to an increase in the phagocytic index in the bulls of the first experimental group by 12.5 % on the 10th day of the experiment relative to the control. On the next day of the experiment, the phagocytic blood index of the bulls of the first experimental group fluctuated between 9.24 ± 0.26 and 9.34 ± 0.30 units.

With the introduction of the liposomal preparation Butaintervit into the organism of animals of the second experimental group, an increase in the phagocytic index was found. Namely, on the 10th and 15th days of the experiment, this indicator increased by 13.1 and 16 % in relation to the control indicators. On the 20th day of the experiment, the studied blood index of the bulls of the second experimental group increased by 21 % compared to the control. On the 30th day of the experiment, the phagocytic index decreased to 9.77 ± 0.21 units.

In the study of the humoral link of the immune system of bulls under an experimental load of cadmium, it was found that the bactericidal activity of the blood serum of bulls of the control group increased slightly on the 5th day of the experiment. However, in the future, in animals of the control group, a decrease in this indicator to 47.5 ± 0.41 % was observed. The lowest bactericidal activity of the blood serum of bulls in the control group was on the 20th day of the experiment.

When feeding the feed additive Metisevit, as well as using the liposomal preparation Butaintervit, the bactericidal activity of blood serum was normalized in animals of both experimental groups. Thus, the bactericidal activity of blood serum in the first experimental group on the 5th day of the experiment increased to 56.6 ± 0.63 %, and in the second – up to 56.9 ± 0.53 %, respectively. Significant changes in this indicator were observed from the 15th day of the experiment in the first experimental group and from the 10th day of the experiment in the second experimental group of animals. On the 20th day of the experiment, an increase in BASK (bactericidal activity of blood serum) was found in the first experimental group by 6.1 % and in the second experimental group by 9.1 % relative to the control (**Table 3**).

The bactericidal activity of blood serum of bulls of the first experimental group on the 30th day of the experiment increased by 4.3 %, and in the second experimental group – by 6.9 % compared with the control group.

When feeding Metisevit to bulls of the first research group, it was found that the lysozyme activity of blood serum in them on the 10th day of the experiment increased by 2.5 % compared to the control group. Subsequently, on the 15th day of the experiment, this indicator in the bulls of the first experimental group decreased slightly, however, compared with the control group, it increased by 2.4 %. On the 30th day of the experiment, the lysozyme activity of the blood serum of the animals of the first experimental group remained probably higher than in the control group (**Table 4**).

Table 3Bactericidal activity of blood serum of bulls under cadmium load and the action of Metisevit and Butaintervit, % ($M \pm m$, $n=5$)

Blood test time (days)	Group of animals		
	Control	Experiment 1 Metisevit	Experiment 2 Metisevit+Butaintervit
Initial values	55.8±0.61	55.9±0.70	55.7±0.63
1 day	55.7±0.43	56.1±0.51	56.6±0.38
5 days	56.4±0.76	56.6±0.63	56.9±0.53
10 days	54.5±0.40	55.8±0.41	57.0±0.61*
15 days	51.6±0.65	54.3±0.60*	56.8±0.54***
20 days	47.5±0.41	53.6±0.52***	56.6±0.42***
30 days	49.5±0.62	53.8±0.58**	56.4±0.60***

Table 4Lysozyme activity of bull blood serum under cadmium load and the action of Metisevit and Butaintervit, % ($M \pm m$, $n=5$)

Blood test time (days)	Group of animals		
	Control	Experiment 1 Metisevit	Experiment 2 Metisevit+Butaintervit
Initial values	22.6±0.42	22.5±0.38	22.7±0.29
1 day	22.8±0.40	22.9±0.39	23.5±0.24
5 days	23.2±0.32	23.4±0.25	23.9±0.33
10 days	20.5±0.55	23.0±0.26*	24.5±0.36**
15 days	20.1±0.28	22.5±0.35**	24.2±0.30***
20 days	19.5±0.61	21.7±0.43*	23.8±0.40***
30 days	20.0±0.22	22.2±0.38**	23.5±0.32***

The introduction of the liposomal preparation Butaintervit to the bulls of the second experimental group contributed to an increase in the lysozyme activity of the blood serum. Namely, on the 10th and 15th days of the experiment, the lysozyme activity of the blood serum of the second experimental group increased by 4 and 4.1 % compared with the control. On the 20th day of the experiment, LASK (serum lysozyme activity) in the blood of the second experimental group decreased slightly compared to the previous day. The lysozyme activity of the blood serum of the second experimental group on the 30th day of the experiment was 23.5±0.32 %, where, compared with the control group, it increased by 3.5 %, respectively.

One of the manifestations of the immune response of the animal organism to the intake of Cadmium is the formation of circulating immune complexes in biological fluids [14].

According to the conducted studies, it was established that the level of circulating immune complexes at the beginning of the experiment fluctuated within the limits of physiological values. Under cadmium load in animals of the control group, the level of CIK (circulating immune complexes) on the 20th day of the experiment increased by 13.5 % relative to the initial values. When the bulls of the first research group of Metisevit were given the level of CIK in their blood, compared with the control, decreased by 8.2 % on the 20th day of the experiment, respectively (Table 5).

Table 5Circulating immune complexes in the blood of bulls under cadmium load and the action of Metisevit and Butaintervit, mmol/l ($M \pm m$, $n=5$)

Blood test time (days)	Group of animals		
	Control	Experiment 1 Metisevit	Experiment 2 Metisevit+Butaintervit
Initial values	67.2±2.04	67.4±1.96	67.3±1.87
1 day	67.8±2.32	67.7±1.92	67.5±1.95
5 days	69.2±2.50	68.3±1.99	67.9±2.10
10 days	72.8±2.30	69.2±2.17	68.3±2.41
15 days	74.6±2.00	69.8±2.00	68.8±2.54
20 days	76.3±2.35	70.0±1.85*	69.4±2.01*
30 days	75.8±2.43	69.8±2.41	69.0±2.50*

The use of bulls of the second experimental group of the preparation Butaintervit contributed to a decrease in the level of the CIK throughout the experiment compared with the control group. On the 20th and 30th days of the experiment, the level of CIK in the blood of this group of animals decreased by 9 % compared with the control group.

Consequently, the liposomal preparation Butaintervit contributed to an increase in the immune status of the body of young cattle under a load of cadmium.

4. Discussion

The function of the immune system of the animal organism is reduced to the recognition of genetically alien antigens and a specific response to them. Its main function is to neutralize and destroy those antigens that stimulate the immune response [15, 16].

Among the many factors that negatively affect the immune defense of the body of young cattle, an important place is occupied by intoxication with heavy metals, which contribute to the formation of toxic metabolic products, which further inhibit the immune system of intoxicated animals [13].

The state of the immune system of the animal organism is assessed by the main immunological tests: BASK, LASK, CIK, FA, FI (Bactericidal activity of blood serum, lysozyme activity of blood serum, circulating immune complexes, phagocytic activity, phagocytic index) [13].

On the basis of the conducted studies, it was found that the cadmium load is accompanied by suppression of the immune system in bulls. The cause of such oppression in cadmium intoxication is the occurrence of immunological deficiency. In our case, immunological deficiency is secondary, since cadmium is its cause.

The research results obtained by us are consistent with the reports of other authors on the immune status of the body of cattle and poultry in terms of toxicosis with heavy metals of various types [17–19].

Therefore, during experimental cadmium loading in young cattle, it is necessary to use such preparations that would correct the state of the immune system. That is why in our studies let's use the liposomal preparation Butaintervit and the feed additive Metisevit.

It should also be noted that according to the studied indicators of nonspecific resistance in young cattle under cadmium load, the combined use of Metisevit and Butaintervit has a better therapeutic effect than the use of Metisevit alone. This is due to the fact that Butaintervit contains butaphosphate, interferon, milk thistle and vitamins. These components of the preparation carried out an effective correction of the nonspecific protection of the body of bulls under a cadmium load. Flavolignans found in milk thistle fail the immunostimulating effect. They were united under the common name – “Silymarin” [20].

The use of interferon as part of the preparation, which improves the efficiency of immune antigen detection, enhances bactericidal and phagocytic activity [21, 22]. The most important biological effect of interferon is an immunomodulatory effect mediated by increased expression of antigens of the major histocompatibility complex of classes I and II; regulation of sensitivity of immunocompetent cells to cytokines; activation of cytotoxic effector cells [21].

The effectiveness of the use of Butaintervit in animals under cadmium load is also indicated by its liposomal form, which exhibits a more pronounced and prolonged effect [23]. Data from a number of studies indicate that liposomes are the best form of preparation carriers in animals [24]

The conducted studies indicate the effectiveness of the use of experimental preparations in animals under conditions of man-made load. When the content of heavy metals in the feed exceeds the maximum allowable concentration, in order to increase the immune status of young cattle, it is advisable to feed the Metisevit feed additive at a dose of 0.36 g/kg of feed and administer Butaintervit intramuscularly at a dose of 5 ml per animal.

In the future, it is planned to study the effect of the liposomal preparation Butaintervit on the antioxidant system of the body of young cattle under conditions of cadmium load.

5. Conclusions

The use of the Metisevit and the liposomal preparation Butaintervit by bulls under a cadmium load showed an increase in the blood levels of the humoral and nonspecific components of the immune system.

With an experimental cadmium load in bulls, the combined use of Metisevit and Butainter-vit had the best effect on the immune system.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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